

KONTRIBUSI PEMBELAJARAN *GUIDED DISCOVERY LEARNING* DAN *LOCUS OF CONTROL* TERHADAP HASIL BELAJAR PRAKTIK HIDROLIKA

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Abstrak

Tujuan penelitian untuk menguji kontribusi pembelajaran dengan pendekatan *guided discovery learning* dan *locus of control* terhadap hasil belajar Praktik Hidrolika. Penelitian menggunakan metode kuantitatif dengan deskriptif korelasional. Populasi penelitian yaitu mahasiswa yang mengikuti mata kuliah Praktik Hidrolika sebanyak 137 orang di Program Studi Teknik Sipil Fakultas Teknik dan Perencanaan Universitas Ekasakti Padang. Sampel penelitian sebanyak 78 orang yang dipilih menggunakan *simple random sampling*. Alat pengumpul data menggunakan angket dan dokumentasi hasil belajar mahasiswa. Data dianalisis menggunakan statistik inferensial dengan regresi ganda. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa: pembelajaran dengan pendekatan *guided discovery learning* berkontribusi signifikan terhadap hasil belajar Praktik Hidrolika; pembelajaran dengan pendekatan *locus of control* berkontribusi signifikan terhadap hasil belajar Praktik Hidrolika; dan pembelajaran dengan pendekatan *guided discovery learning* dan *locus of control* secara bersama-sama berkontribusi signifikan terhadap hasil belajar Praktik Hidrolika.

Keywords: *guided discovery learning, locus of control, hasil belajar.*

Abstract

The purpose of the research was to examine the contribution of learning with guided discovery learning and locus of control on learning outcomes for Hydraulic Practice. The research used quantitative methods with correlational descriptive. The research population was 137 students who took the Hydraulics Practice course in the Civil Engineering Study Program, Faculty of Engineering and Planning of Ekasakti University Padang. The research sample was 78 people who were selected using simple random sampling. Data collection tools used questionnaires and documentation of student learning outcomes. Data were analyzed using inferential statistics with multiple regression. The results showed that: the learning process with the guided discovery learning approach contributed significantly to the learning outcomes of Hydraulic Practice; the learning process with a locus of control approach contributes significantly to learning outcomes in Hydraulics Practice; and learning process with the guided discovery learning and locus of control as in aggregate significantly contribute to the learning outcomes of Hydraulic Practice.

Keywords: *guided discovery learning, locus of control, learning outcomes.*